

Role of Predatory Nematodes in Bio-Management of Plant Parasitic Nematodes

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Abstract

Plant-parasitic nematodes are prey for predatory nematodes, which feed on soil microbes. Because of their persistent connection with plant-parasitic nematodes in the rhizosphere, they lower populations of plant-parasitic nematodes in practically all soils, and they also release nutrients in plant-available forms, which may help plants better bear nematode burden on their roots. The predation of plant parasite nematodes by nematodes of the orders Mononchida, Diplogasterida, Dorylaímida, and aphelenchida has been examined. However, the evidence available in field/natural circumstances is insufficient to infer whether they are efficient biocontrol agents. Diplogasterids, on the other hand, are the best predators for nematode biocontrol because of their short life cycles, ease of culture, prey-specificity, chemotaxis sensing, and tolerance to harsh circumstances.

Keywords: Bio-agents, Bio-control, Plant-parasitic nematodes, Predatory nematodes

Introduction

In sustainable agriculture, biocontrol agents are an appealing option for managing pests and diseases of crops. Biocontrol may be an effective, cost-effective, and environmentally responsible way to manage pests. Predatory nematodes are one of the biocontrol agents that can be very useful in the management of plant-parasitic nematodes. Predatory nematodes are divided into four families based on their feeding equipment and methods: mononchids, diplogasterids, dorylaímids, and aphelenchids (Table 1). Each group has a separate feeding device, as well as a different feeding mechanism and food preference. Mononchids have a well-developed buccal cavity containing teeth and denticles, as well as a well-developed buccal muscle. They have a feeding apparatus that cuts, sucks, and swallows. Dorylaímids have a piercing and sucking buccal cavity that is provided with a dagger-shaped odontostyle. Diplogasteridae have a tiny buccal cavity with teeth of various sizes and locations (Bilgrami and Brey, 2005). They have sucking and cutting feeding devices. aphelenchids have short, narrow spears with no basal knobs that they utilize to pierce and suck the prey's bodily content. Predatory nematodes have a five-step prey capture and feeding mechanism: interaction with

prey, attack reaction, attack, salivation, and extracorporeal digestion and ingestion (Fig. 1). Mononchids have little prey specialization, but diplogasterids and aphelenchids do. For predatory nematodes found in diplogasterid predators, a high reproductive capacity and a short life cycle are considered good characteristics.

Table 1. Important families and genera of predatory nematodes

Families	Genera
Mononchids	<i>anatonchus, Clarkus, Coomansus, Íotonchus, Miconchus, Mononchus, Prionchulus, Sporonchulus</i> etc.
Diplogasterid	<i>Butlerius, Diplogaster, Mononchoides, Odontopharynx</i> etc.
Dorylaímids	<i>allodorylaímus, aporcelaímellus, aporcelaímus, aquatídes, Díscolaímus, Eudorylaímus, Neoactínolaímus</i> etc.
aphelenchid	<i>Seínura</i> etc.

Fig. 1. Feeding of predatory nematode on prey

Factors affecting biocontrol efficiency

Prey range:

Predatory nematodes feed on a variety of nematode species as well as other creatures (Table 2). Because plant-parasitic nematodes are found in poly-specific communities alongside other nematodes and soil organisms, this may make them less effective bio-agents against nematode pests.

Table 2. Predation efficiency of predatory nematode and prey density of plant-parasitic nematodes

Predator	Prey	Reference
<i>Mononchoïdes longicaudatus</i> and <i>M. fortidens</i>	The number of preys killed by <i>M. fortidens</i> and <i>M. longicaudatus</i> grew in tandem with the increase in prey populations. <i>Meloidogyne incognita</i> and <i>Hirschmanniella oryzae</i> predation peaked at 200 J2.	Bilgrami and Jaïrajpurí (1989)
<i>Mylonchulus dentatus</i>	When the number of <i>M. incognita</i> individuals grew from few to many, more preys were killed.	Bilgrami and Kulshreshtha (1993)
<i>Mononchoïdes gaugleri</i>	On <i>M. incognita</i> , predation rate and feeding duration were influenced by prey density.	Bilgrami et al. (2005)
<i>Fíctor compostícola</i>	<i>F. compostícola's</i> predation efficacy on <i>aphelenchoïdes avenae</i> , <i>avena swarupí</i> , <i>Ditylenchus myceliophagus</i> , <i>Panagrolaimus</i> sp., and <i>Bursilla</i> sp. rose as population increased.	Keshari (2016)
<i>F. compostícola</i>	With an increase in prey density from 250 to 2000, the predation effectiveness of <i>F. compostícola</i> on <i>M. incognita</i> J2 improved.	Sídhú and Kanwar (2019)

Host preference (Prey):

Prey selection or preference may differ depending on predator species. A predatory nematode is selective in its feeding and does not feed on all species of nematodes. *Helicotylenchus dihystra*, *Hemícriconemoïds*, immature females of *R. reniformis*, *Zeldia* sp., and *Díploghastrelus gracilis* were not fed by *F. compostícola*. Females of *Helicotylenchus dihystra*, J2 of *Heterodera avenae*, *H. cajaní*, *H. sorghí*, *H. zae*, *Longidorus* sp., J2 of *M.*

gramínicola, females of *M. incognita*, and females of *M. javanica* were not fed by *S. paratenuicaudata*. To evaluate prey preference, a predator is presented with two or more prey species at the same time, and the number of each prey left after a certain amount of time is recorded. *F. composticola* preferred *aphelenchus avenae*, *D. myceliophagus*, *a. swarupí*, and *Bursilla* sp. in combinations of two, three, and four prey species, according to Keshari (2016). In all of the combinations, she discovered that *D. myceliophagus* was the most favored species, followed by *H. avenae*, and *Bursilla* sp. was the least preferred.

Host population density:

The rate of predation is affected by prey density, with higher prey density increasing the probability of encounters. *D. colobocercus*, *a. thornei*, *M. longicaudatus*, and *M. fortidensis* predation rates were proportionate to prey density. In most investigations, predation efficiency rose as density increased. However, given a specific prey-predator combination, it should reach a maximum at some point (Keshari, 2016). It may vary by prey species for predatory nematodes, and it may vary by a predator on a single prey species for different predators.

Nutrition:

The nematode's development and reproduction are influenced by the quality and quantity of food they consume. *F. composticola* does not reproduce unless it is fed. *S. paratenuicaudata* can feed on a variety of nematode species and deposit eggs, according to Vats *et al.* (2004). It ate *Mylonchulus* sp. but was unable to reproduce. It generated sterile eggs that did not hatch and turned brown after feeding on J2 of *anguina tritici* and *Subanguina chrysopogoni*. As a result, predators eating on such preys will lower their numbers. Some predatory nematodes feed on bacteria and other species, which will undoubtedly reduce their effectiveness against nematode pests.

Biological enemies:

Every organism in the natural world has natural enemies, and predatory nematodes are no exception. On this subject, there is just a little amount of work available. Thorne (1927) discovered apicomplexa parasite infection in various mononchid species, which he attributed to a decrease in their population. In lab investigations, predatory nematodes have been observed feeding on another predatory nematode. *S. paratenuicaudata* was found feeding on *F.*

compostícola by Vats *et al.* (2004). *F. compostícola* was shown to feed on *Nygotiaimus harishí* and *aporcelaímium* sp., reducing their populations in agar plates, according to Keshari (2016).

Age and gender of predatory nematodes:

When compared to larval stages, adults kill a greater quantity of preys. *Díplonteron colobocercus* males hunted more than females because females had a higher strike rate than males and they dined on prey for longer periods of time (Keshari, 2016).

Cannibalism:

It is a phenomenon in which a species feeds on members of its own species. When there is a scarcity of food, some predators exhibit this behavior (prey). Some predatory nematodes have been found to have it (Bilgrami and Brey, 2005). This is a negative characteristic because it reduces the predator population. This could be a survival and sustenance strategy, as it aids the organism's survival in the face of food scarcity.

Environmental and edaphic factors:

The life cycle, development, reproduction, and survival of nematodes are all influenced by temperature. The activity of predators and prey is influenced by temperature, which results in a decrease in the rate of predation by *M. aquaticus*. Diplogasterid predators prefer temperatures between 25 and 30 °C. At temperatures of 25 to 30 °C, *D. sternalis* preying capacity was at its peak (Shafiqat *et al.*, 1987). *F. compostícola* is active between 20 and 35 degrees Celsius, however, its activity decreases as the temperature rises. at 20 to 35 °C, *S. paratenuicaudata* fed and reproduced, with maximal reproduction between 30 °C, but did not feed or multiply at 10 and 15 °C (Vats *et al.*, 2004). another important factor for predatory nematode survival is soil moisture. They should be able to endure a wide range of moisture in order to be effective as biocontrol agents. Mononchids are most commonly found in damp soil. Mononchids were found around the plant roots when the pH was between 5.78 and 6.58, the soil temperature was between 20.6 and 23.0 °C, the moisture level was between 17.71 and 24.53 percent, and the organic carbon content was between 3.06 and 4.28 percent, according to Sharma and Gupta (2015). There isn't a lot of research on the effects of salts on predatory nematodes.

Conclusion and future prospects:

Under field conditions, the impact of predatory nematodes as a biocontrol agent may rise during the peak season of endoparasitic nematode hatching/emergence. However, the efficacy and long-term advantages to crop production will determine whether or not this technique can be implemented as a successful nematode management strategy. To find and disseminate this ecologically friendly nematode pest management strategy, more research, development, and extension efforts are needed. The first aim is to determine the diversity of predatory species found in various agro-climatic areas. Identification and characterization of predatory nematode species that are well adapted to local conditions, as well as the development of sustainable methodologies for mass culturing, formulation, and time and mode of application, should all be part of the effort.

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